

**ORGANIZING THE INDEPENDENT EDUCATION OF STUDENTS IN
HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS ON THE BASIS OF
A CREATIVE APPROACH**

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Abstract. Today, there is a sufficient pedagogical need to organize the independent education of students of higher education institutions based on a creative approach. Therefore, the development of independent education based on creativity is one of the urgent research issues. This article examines the specific features of organizing independent education based on a creative approach. At the same time, the didactic possibilities of organizing independent education on the basis of creativity are highlighted. In addition, special attention is paid to the methods, factors and basic conditions of organizing independent education based on a creative approach in the preparation of future specialists as educated, qualified and mature individuals.

Key words: Independent education, creativity, creative approach, creativity skills, factors that develop creativity, creative teaching methods, project-based teaching, problem-based research methods, methods of using new information and communication technologies.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the education system in the world is developing rapidly, and this is positively causing significant changes in the field of science. The development of the world education system is primarily the main idea of the educational model presented at the World Economic Forum "4K: critical thinking, creativity, communication, collaboration (leadership)" skills in any type of activity. is inextricably linked. At the same time, the formation of these skills in future teachers in the field of education has been tested in many developed countries and has shown its effectiveness. Therefore, every country in the world is organizing not only the education system, but also every sphere of human activity based on the 4K model. All the skills of the 4K model are interrelated and serve for the comprehensive development of future teachers in the field of education.

It is known that in countries such as Canada, Germany, USA, Russia, Finland, Korea, Japan, which are at the forefront of education system development in the world, the teaching process is being organized on the basis of this approach which is the second skill of the above model and this approach shows that every link in the field of education is closely related to the concept of creativity. Therefore, this situation was observed and analyzed, and as a result, the organization of every field of the education system on the basis of innovation and creativity began in Uzbekistan. But this approach

did not include all departments of the education sector. For example: Today, the low organization of students' independent education based on a creative approach in higher education institutions may cause the loss of students' creative thinking, thinking and creativity in the future. Therefore, organizing independent education of higher education students based on a creative approach is one of the urgent issues of the day.

Therefore, forming critical and creative thinking, creativity skills of students through independent education in the higher education system and organizing this process using the main methods and factors of creative approach is one of the main tasks of today.

Literature analysis

In order to form the qualities of creativity in future teachers through independent education, we must first of all dwell on the content of the concept of creativity. Creativity (lat., ing. "create" - creation, "creative" - creator) is a creative ability that describes the readiness of an individual to produce new ideas and is part of talent as an independent factor. Creativity means a person's creative ability to create new things and solve problems. It is based on originality, practicality, unusualness and freedom [1]. A person's creativity is manifested in his thinking, communication, feelings, and certain types of activities. Creativity describes a person as a whole or his specific features, mental sharpness. Also, creativity is reflected as an important factor of talent.

The famous scientist Paul Torrance, who is considered the "father of creativity", distinguished four creativity skills[2]. According to the results of his research, it is possible to form these creative skills and evaluate them:

Fig. 1. Creativity skills

In the last 5 years, many studies have been conducted on the organization of the educational process based on a creative approach in higher education institutions. All these studies serve to increase the creativity of students. Among them, B.N. Kurbanova

in her work "Creative independent education is a type of learning from subjects in educational institutions, in which students consciously apply one or another tasks, goals, based on different educational methods, based on a creative approach to themselves. is determined by his ability to plan and implement his work and self-evaluation" [3]. From these points, it is clear that independent education organized on the basis of a correct, creative approach - enables the student to work independently on himself, to be creative, to develop self-control skills and opportunities, his professional It is one of the important processes that helps to develop, activates, enriches and strengthens acquired knowledge and encourages independent, critical thinking. In this process, the student is at the center and he works independently without a teacher. The student is involved throughout the process. The professor invites the student to actively participate.

Research methodology

Independent education in higher education institutions is a process which is aimed at deepening the knowledge of students, forming an interest in creative activities, creating a basis for engaging in research or methodical activities, forming independence in educational activities, forming creativity together with conscious understanding and independent, creative, critical thinking, is a process that serves to develop creative abilities. In order to form all these in students, it is necessary to organize independent education based on a correct and creative approach. The concept of creativity should be an integral part of all other educational processes, not only in the independent education process.

When organizing independent education of students in higher education institutions based on a creative approach, special attention should be paid to the following situations:

- orientation of the subject of independent work to a certain problem; (the student tries to think creatively when solving a problem, and creativity is formed in him, the ability to find a solution to a problem is formed)
- taking into account the requirements of the state and society;
- the introduction of small inventions or discoveries (for example: create a new method that develops the student's logical thinking), the introduction of a number of interesting activities, examples, problems, etc.;
- each independent education leads to the development of the student's creativity and creative search;
- based on experience, laboratory testing or other creative practice;
- to create internal learning motivation - this means that the student believes in the power of creativity, puts a high value on himself. On this basis, the need and interest of the future teacher is awakened not only in knowledge, but also in relation to the process itself. Emotional uplift has a positive effect on any student;
- to create a favorable psychological climate - to create conditions that have a positive effect on the development of various abilities of students. (Encouraging the aspirations of future teachers for creative work, making them confident in their capabilities, respecting their opinions, interests, abilities, and the work they have done);
- to provide proper pedagogical support to the student; (To fulfill the given task - the teacher should introduce the list of necessary literature to the student and

adequately answer the questions that appear in them)

- to carry out various works together; (According to the level of complexity of independent education, it should be carried out in a group form. In this process, students mainly develop cooperation skills and creativity)

- to pay great attention to independent execution of creative assignments; (give the student appropriate assignments so that he can complete assignments independently, use his abilities as much as possible, slowly rise to this peak, and not lose interest and aspiration for creative activity)

- paying attention to consistency and systematicity in the development of students' creative abilities; (Disruptive organization of creative tasks does not help to develop their creative activity and does not affect the development of creative abilities. It is necessary to find ways to develop creative abilities from the point of view of the uniqueness of each person. For this, a professor teacher it is necessary for the student to develop these skills.)

- the diversity of the creative assignment according to the content and level; (giving creative independent education in an easier form depending on the stage of the student)

- to consider interdisciplinarity; (This process creates an atmosphere of success. That is, in the process of solving creative tasks, applying knowledge of various disciplines, comparing with each other, and being able to draw positive conclusions from them will grow them sufficiently)

Beneficial aspects of the correct and creative organization of independent education for students are manifested in the following:

- Focusing on creative work;
- Consideration of previously acquired knowledge;
- Information of connection between practice and theory;
- Adjustment of study intensity to the needs of the learner;
- Support of the learner's initiative and responsibility;
- Creation of grounds for engaging in research or methodical activities;
- Development of creative abilities of conscious understanding and independent, creative, critical thinking;
- Formation of interest in creative activity;
- Deepening and expanding knowledge;
- The most important thing is the formation of creativity in students;

Encouraging students to think creatively in the process of self-learning forms the habit of creative thinking in them. In addition, it motivates them to solve the problem, change their worldview positively, engage in a rational attitude and develop empathy. The inextricable connection between creative thinking and a person's intellect makes a great contribution to the development of his self-confidence, mental qualities, creativity, and the qualities that show his creative potential.

Fig. 1. Necessary factors that develop creative thinking of future teachers in the process of independent education

The most effective methods of independent work of students in a creative approach include methods that help increase the intensity of the learning process:

- 1) Project-based teaching methods;
- 2) Problematic search methods;
- 3) The method of using the latest information and communication technologies;
- 4) Methods of collective mental activity.

Using the project-based learning method, students can get predictable results of their independent work. This method requires advance preparation from the student. Therefore, it is recommended to use this method for 3-4 year students.

The main requirements for using the project method:

- individual and collective activities of students;
- setting a problem that requires comprehensive knowledge of students in planning the actions necessary to solve them;
- use of research methods;
- creating a project work plan;
- project work;
- recording and analysis of intermediate results;
- identification, analysis and practical significance of final results[4].

Problem search methods are aimed at increasing students' knowledge activity. Using these methods increases motivation, logical thinking, increases creativity and encourages students to do independent research.

For students, it is recommended to use collective mental activity methods to solve problems with a high level of complexity. The use of these methods helps to develop creative thinking, to increase the level of intellectual development, to form teamwork skills, to identify students' creative abilities, and to increase their independence and

cooperation. Collective mental activity methods are distinguished from other methods by their novelty, complex approach to problem solving, greater mobility in choosing problem solving directions, and active creativity of all participants.

The methods and forms of computer technology increase the efficiency of students' learning of educational material, help to develop students' creative and mental abilities, increase their activity and interest in acquiring knowledge. The use of information technology in the organization of students' independent work has the following methodological approaches: differential and systematic. A differential approach to education can significantly expand the availability and quality of education, the adoption of the latest technologies, which helps to strengthen the role of independent work of students in the educational process. A systematic approach to the organization of students' independent work ensures the consistency and structural-functional connection of the educational material. Information technologies that provide students with the use of non-traditional sources of information, enable the implementation of new forms and methods of teaching, and expand the opportunities to acquire and strengthen practical skills are of particular importance.[4]

Summary

To sum up, today the role of independent education in producing highly qualified specialists who are well-educated, advanced, mature, able to think clearly and meaningfully is incomparable. Independent education plays a fundamental role in the process of raising a mature person. As it can be seen from the speeches above, this study mainly provided information about the methods of organizing independent education in a creative approach, factors of its development, its important aspects, and useful aspects for students. All these are methods used in the developed countries of the world, and it is recommended to use them in the educational process in Uzbekistan

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